

FIBER REINFORCED POLYMER BRIDGE DECKS FOR LIFT BRIDGE REHABILITATION

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INTRODUCTION

Advanced fiber reinforced polymer (FRP) composite materials are seeing greater use in civil infrastructure and bridge rehabilitation because of their excellent specific stiffness and strength properties. While many projects involving the use of fiberglass reinforced polymer bridge decks have been successfully applied over the past decade, one of the first applications of carbon fibers in bridge deck panels of a heavily traveled lift bridge will be completed in 2003.

The 55 years old Schuyler Heim Bridge, shown in Figure 1, is the largest vertical lift bridge on the west coast. The bridge is located in the Port of Los Angeles and serves as a critical traffic link for local commerce between the city of Long Beach and Terminal Island. The traffic on the bridge is mostly heavy trucks carrying cargo containers to and from the shipping ports. As a result of the heavy loads, the existing deck made of welded steel grating has been in continuous distress despite a complete replacement in 1997.

a). Overall view

b). Steel grate panels of lift section

Figure 1. Schuyler Heim Lift Bridge in Long Beach, CA.

Stress cracks in the welds of the 5-inch deep open gratings, Figure 2, have resulted in reduced strength, excessive noise and vibration, and regular lane closure on the lift span. Repairing these failures is proving to be a continuous and hence very costly maintenance problem for Caltrans

Figure 2. Typical fatigue cracking and weld failures on existing steel grates.

In 1997 the California Department of Transportation (Caltrans) launched a trial project to replace some of the steel grating with solid deck panels made of polymer composite materials at the most distressed locations. *Martin Marietta Composites* (Raleigh, NC), together with engineering subcontractors *Parsons Transportation Group* (San Francisco, CA) and *Dumlao Consulting* (Pleasanton, CA), were awarded the project (Reference 1) to design and deliver the composite deck panels for installation scheduled for first half of 2003. This paper discusses the polymer composite bridge deck design developed for the program including: performance criteria; design features and fabrication of the deck panels.

DESIGN AND PERFORMANCE CRITERIA

PHYSICAL REQUIREMENTS - Weight is one of the important drivers that make composite materials attractive for this application. The replacement decks cannot exceed the physical limits dictated by the existing lift system and support structure, namely:

- Attach to existing support girders spaced 4-feet apart
- Nominal panel weight cannot exceed 22 lb/ft² (including wear surface)
- Total height of the deck above existing support stringers cannot exceed 5-3/16"
- Mount onto existing stringers and curbs.

FUTURE PERFORMANCE REQUIREMENTS - Caltrans took into consideration the future demands of the bridge and defined the design requirements around the AASHTO (American Association of State Highway and Transportation Officials) HS-25 bridge load specifications versus the current HS-20 specifications under which most existing bridges have been designed. This translates to more stringent design requirements for deflection and load envelopes the composite decks must support

- Girder spacing/deflection > 500 (less than .096" vertical deflection on 4-foot girder spacing under 26,000 lb wheel load)
- HS-25 wheel load + 1.3 impact factor (equivalent to 26,000 lb applied on a 9"x20"foot print)
- Ultimate Factor of safety > 4.0
- Height limit 5-3/32" and weight not to exceed 22 lb/ft²

The HS-25 performance standards are 25% higher than the HS-20 requirement. The higher loads and the desire to maintain the same absolute deflection criteria amount to a 4 times higher stiffness requirement for the composites deck versus typical steel grate deck.

COMPOSITE PANEL DESIGN CONCEPT

STIFFNESS DRIVEN - To meet the bending stiffness and stay within the project budget, a hybrid composite deck concept was developed incorporating high modulus carbon fibers with lower cost fiberglass fibers. Figure 3 and Figure 4 show the specific details, taken from Reference 2, of the typical composite panel for the Schuyler Heim Bridge. The panel average weight is about 17.5 lb/ft² for a total weight of 3700 lb per 35'x6' deck without wear surface.

SANDWICH PROFILE TO MAXIMIZE STIFFNESS TO WEIGHT - At the time the design was developed, the decision was made to use readily available components and raw materials to stay within the program budget. For cost reasons, every effort was made to “engineer” the geometry of the deck with a cross section that could be readily constructed with commercially available materials. Thus, the deck employs a sandwich construction consisting of commercially pultruded square fiberglass tube members bonded together to form the continuous core of the panel. Most of the design effort to maximize stiffness was placed on optimizing the material and laminate construction over the established core.

Carbon and fiberglass reinforced fabric are laminated to the flats of the pultruded core assembly. The carbon fibers laminates are the principal stiffening element of the design, and are laminated in a biased ratio of 2:1 in the transverse/longitudinal directions (see Figure 4 for details). The base lay-up consists of 56 oz quasi –isotropic fiberglass (EQX) and 21 oz unidirectional carbon (C-LR) fabrics applied wet by hand lay-up. The base resin used for the facesheet is an epoxy vinyl ester resin, Dow Chemicals’ Derekane 411-350, which is a lower cost alternative to epoxies.

INCREASING SECTION THICKNESS - Earlier parametric studies revealed that just adding carbon fibers to the top and bottom facesheets of the 4” core would not be sufficient to achieve the needed bending stiffness while keeping below 22 lb/ft², with wear surface. Thus, to further increase the stiffness a 2” drop-down section was added to increase the section in the clear span between stringers. Closed cell urethane foam sheets, 6 lb/ft³ density, 2” thick, are used in the 3-foot wide drop-down between girders (see Figures 3 and 7d). Additional unidirectional carbon fiber reinforcements are laminated to the bottom of the drop-down to further stiffen the mid-span bending stiffness.

TOP DOWN INSTALLATION – Much of the design effort focused on one other critical design issue; installing and securing the composite decks to the existing super structure. The three critical connections are:

- The connections that secure the panels to the superstructure stringers;
- The method of interlocking adjacent panels for effective shear transfer, and
- An effective method of installation without the need to work from below.

These design challenges were resolved by modifying connection techniques already in use in the bridge industry. Details will be discussed later, under INSTALLATION PROCEDURE.

Figure 3. General FRP composite deck panel for the Schuyler Heim Bridge.

Figure 4. Composite laminate detail.

PERFORMANCE VERIFICATION

VALIDATION PROCESS – Numerical analysis and laboratory tests were used to validate the deck design (Reference 3). Numerical methods employing several techniques including Finite Element analysis (Reference 1 and 6) were used to determine stiffness, predicted failure mode, and ultimate strength capabilities of the composite deck system. Materials testing of the engineered laminates were also performed to verify laminate properties and to fine-tune the simulation analyses. The derived mechanical properties of the hybrid carbon/fiberglass reinforced facesheet are presented in Table 1.

STRUCTURAL TESTING - The final step in validating the design before manufacturing was the fabrication of four fully featured prototype decks that were tested to ultimate capacity under simulated wheel loads. These tests were conducted at *California State University at Fullerton* (CSUF), and at the *University of California at Irvine* (UCI), CA. The test suite consisted of four specimens: the first two were single span, 4-foot long; and the last two were multi-span specimens, 10-foot long by 3-foot wide.

DESIGN REQUIREMENTS EXCEEDED - In the multi-span tests, the 10-foot by 3 feet multi-span test decks shown in Figure 5. were subjected to simulated wheel loads to ultimate capacity. Two specimens were tested, one without and the other with a 3/8-inch thick polymer concrete wear surface installed.

The results of the tests are shown in Figure 6. In both tests the deck were loaded up to HS-25 maximum wheel load (26 kips) before initial weakening became evident in the form of “softening” of the load versus deflection curve. The decks were then inspected while the design load was held constant, and no failure was observed. The decks behaved linearly in the design range, which translated to an L/D of 650 and 575 for the specimen without and specimen with wear surface, respectively -- both exceeded the

minimum L/D of 500. Figure 5 also shows the ultimate load capacity of the test specimens exceeded the 104 kips minimum required for an ultimate Factor of Safety greater than 4.

REPAIRABILITY DEMONSTRATION – Part of the design verification included a demonstration of damage repair. A damaged test deck was successfully repaired using industry standard repair practice and the repaired specimen was tested to higher failure loads than in its original state. For details the reader is directed to Reference 7.

Table 1. Laminate properties of the carbon-fiberglass/poylmer hybrid facesheets.

Calculated Mechanical Properties for Hybrid Facesheet Laminate.		
Physical Property	Transverse (90 °) Direction	Longitudinal (0°) Direction
Tension		
Ultimate Strength (ksi)	73.0	51.4
Directional Modulus (msi)	3.65	2.57
Strain to Failure (% in/in)	2.0	2.0
Compression		
Ultimate Strength (ksi)	36.00	
Directional Modulus (msi)	3.65	
Strain to Failure (in/in)	1.0	
In-plane shear		
Ultimate Strength (ksi)	14.00	14.4
Directional Modulus (msi)	0.57	0.55
Strain to Failure (in/in)	3.91	4.38
Flexural		
Ultimate Strength (ksi)	50.50 / 58.8	40.30 / 43.2
Directional Modulus (msi)	2.47	1.92
Strain to Failure (in/in)	2.56 / 3.07	2.92 / 2.95
Interlaminar Shear (ksi)	3.68	2.19
Coefficient of Thermal Expansion (in/in/°F)	7.2×10^{-6}	12.1×10^{-6}
Poisson's Ratio	.316	.180
Nominal Thickness (in)	.30 – 3.2	
Densities (lb/in³)		
• Carbon Fiber	.065	
• Fiberglass Fiber	.095	
• Resin Matrix	.038	
• Laminate [0/0/0/0/0]	.053	
Fiber Volume (%)	35.0	
Glass Transition (T_g) (D.S.C.)	250.0 °F	

Figure 5. Full size multi-span specimen for strength testing.

Figure 6. Load versus deflection results for multi-span tests.

DECK PANEL FABRICATION

Eight deck panels were manufactured for this project, consisting of: six 6' x 35' main panels (see Figure 3.) and two 4'-6"x 35' end panels. The simple, flat profile allowed conventional hand lay-up technique to be employed. The procedure followed for each panel is as follows:

Fabrication procedure:

- Pultruded core members bonded to form core panel
- Bottom facesheet is laminated first by hand lay-up
- Foam dropdown sections bonded to bottom face and reinforced by extra carbon sheets
- Panel is flipped and top is laminated by hand lay-up
- Connection holes are bored
- Edge channels laminate and trimmed
- Connection keys fabricated by VARTM
- Connection key bonded into edge channel
- Final trimming and tagging
- Trial fit-up
- Panels are instrumented and inspected
- 3/8" polymer concrete wear surface is applied
- Panels are shipped

Figures 7 show the wet lay-up fabrication process steps of the typical panel. The pultruded core tubes are first bonded together to form the core panel. The faces of the core assembly are then prepared for lamination, bottom face first. Material is laminated to the faces in the order detailed in Figure 4.

Following the lamination process, the panel is moved to the finishing area, trimmed and the anchor holes are cored through the top and bottom facesheets, as shown in Figure 8. At this time the shear keys are fabricated by resin infusion molding using hard molds, and then are bonded to the decks. Secondary closeouts and field monitoring gages are installed as well.

After all secondary hardware installation is completed, the decks are inspected and, lastly, polymer concrete wear surface is screed onto the top surface, as shown in figure 9. This completes the manufacturing of the decks which have been delivered Caltrans

Figure 7. Composite deck panel fabrication, wet-lay-up sequence.

Figure 8. Deck panel detail finishing and instrumentation.

k). NDE inspection (tap test shown)

l). Polymer concrete wear surface applied

m). Deck are labeled and packed

n). Deck delivered to Terminal Island

**Figure 9.
Deck panel inspection and wear surface installation.**

INSTALLATION PROCEDURE

DECK TO GIRDER CONNECTION

A bolted connection will be used to anchor the deck panels to the bridge girders as illustrated in Figure 10. Instead of conventional bolts, 3/4" diameter threaded Nelson Studs will be resistance welded to the top of the girders through anchor holes drilled into the deck. The holes are drilled through the finished facesheets of deck at the fabrication plant. The lower hole is slightly larger than the threaded stud to allow lock-down by a torque nut. The top hole is 3" in diameter to allow tool access during installation as illustrated in Figure 10. A photograph of a connection as-tested is shown at the lower right corner.

The deck will be secured using conventional, Caltrans approved, structural washers and industrial nuts with anaerobic thread locking. The top hole will then be sealed with a bonded cover and polymer concrete overlay.

A pair of studs is used for each connection to prevent transverse rolling at the joints. The elastomeric pad between the stringers and deck serves to distribute loads and provide flexibility for the deck to grow with temperature and moisture changes. It also serves to provide a damping interface to minimize fatigue wear and damage from direct deck to stringer contact.

DECK TO DECK CONNECTION- After a deck is placed and secured to the stringer, the next deck is lowered in place. Epoxy paste adhesive is then smeared on the tongue and groove shear key and channel surfaces. The deck is slid and mated to the previous deck and the Nelson studs are installed as illustrated in 6.

CONCLUSION

The composite deck panels have been manufactured and delivered to Caltrans for installation at an as yet undetermined time in the first half of 2003. Because of the severity of degradation in the current steel grate decking, Caltrans has decided to replace all of the decking with new grates except for the section slated for replacement by the carbon-fiberglass/polymer decks. The Schuyler Heim Bridge will serve as

an excellent test-bed for one-on-one evaluation of composite decks versus steel grate decks after installation is completed.

Figure 10. Deck-girder anchor and deck-deck shear connections.

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